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**Conjectures Which Generalize
Andrica's Conjecture**

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CONJECTURES WHICH GENERALIZE ANDRICA'S CONJECTURE

Five conjectures on pairs of consecutive primes are listed below with examples in each case.

1) The equation $p_{n+1}^x - p_n^x = 1$, (1)
 where p_n is the n -th prime, has a unique solution situated in between 0.5 and 1. Checking the first 168 prime numbers (less than 1000), one gets that:

- the maximum occurs of course for $n=1$, i.e.

$$3^x - 2^x = 1 \text{ when } x=1.$$

- the minimum occurs for $n=31$, i.e.

$$127^x - 113^x = 1 \text{ when } x = 0.567148... = a_0. \quad (2)$$

Thus, Andrica's Conjecture

$$A_n = \sqrt{p_{n+1}} - \sqrt{p_n} < 1,$$

is generalized to

$$2) \quad B_n = p_{n+1}^a - p_n^a < 1, \text{ where } a < a_0. \quad (3)$$

It is remarkable that the minimum x doesn't occur for $11^x - 7^x = 1$

as in Andrica's Conjecture the maximum value, but in (2).

Also, the function B_n in (3) is falling asymptotically as A_n in (2). Look at these prime exponential equations solved with a TI-92 Graphing Calculator (approximately: the bigger the prime number gap is, the smaller solution x for the equation (1);

for the same gap between two consecutive primes, the larger the primes, the bigger x):

$$3^x - 2^x = 1, \text{ has the solution } x = 1.000000.$$

$$5^x - 3^x = 1, \text{ has the solution } x \approx 0.727160.$$

$$7^x - 5^x = 1, \text{ has the solution } x \approx 0.763203.$$

$$11^x - 7^x = 1, \text{ has the solution } x \approx 0.599669.$$

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- $13^x - 11^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.807162$.
 $17^x - 13^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.647855$.
 $19^x - 17^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.826203$.
 $29^x - 23^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.604284$.
 $37^x - 31^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.624992$.
 $97^x - 89^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.638942$.
 $127^x - 113^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.567148$.
 $149^x - 139^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.629722$.
 $191^x - 181^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.643672$.
 $223^x - 211^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.625357$.
 $307^x - 293^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.620871$.
 $331^x - 317^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.624822$.
 $497^x - 467^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.663219$.
 $521^x - 509^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.666917$.
 $541^x - 523^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.616550$.
 $751^x - 743^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.732706$.
 $787^x - 773^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.664972$.
 $853^x - 839^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.668274$.
 $877^x - 863^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.669397$.
 $907^x - 887^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.627848$.
 $967^x - 953^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.673292$.
 $997^x - 991^x = 1$, has the solution $x \approx 0.776959$.

If $x > a_0$, the difference of x -powers of consecutive primes is normally greater than 1. Checking more versions:

$$\begin{array}{rcl}
 3^{0.99} & - & 2^{0.99} \approx 0.981037. \\
 11^{0.99} & - & 7^{0.99} \approx 3.874270. \\
 11^{0.60} & - & 7^{0.60} \approx 1.001270. \\
 11^{0.59} & - & 7^{0.59} \approx 0.963334. \\
 11^{0.55} & - & 7^{0.55} \approx 0.822980. \\
 11^{0.50} & - & 7^{0.50} \approx 0.670873.
 \end{array}$$

$$389^{0.99} - 383^{0.99} \approx 5.596550.$$

$$\begin{array}{rcl}
 11^{0.599} & - & 7^{0.599} \approx 0.997426. \\
 17^{0.599} & - & 13^{0.599} \approx 0.810218. \\
 37^{0.599} & - & 31^{0.599} \approx 0.874526. \\
 127^{0.599} & - & 113^{0.599} \approx 1.230100.
 \end{array}$$

$$997^{0.599} \quad - \quad 991^{0.599} \approx 0.225749.$$

$$127^{0.5} \quad - \quad 113^{0.5} \approx 0.639282.$$

3) $C_n = p_{n+1}^{1/k} - p_n^{1/k} < 2/k$, where p_n is the n -th prime, and $k \geq 2$ is an integer.

$11^{1/2}$	-	$7^{1/2}$	$\approx 0.670873.$
$11^{1/4}$	-	$7^{1/4}$	$\approx 0.1945837251.$
$11^{1/5}$	-	$7^{1/5}$	$\approx 0.1396211046.$
$127^{1/5}$	-	$113^{1/5}$	$\approx 0.060837.$
$3^{1/2}$	-	$2^{1/2}$	$\approx 0.317837.$
$3^{1/3}$	-	$2^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.1823285204.$
$5^{1/3}$	-	$3^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.2677263764.$
$7^{1/3}$	-	$5^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.2029552361.$
$11^{1/3}$	-	$7^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.3110489078.$
$13^{1/3}$	-	$11^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.1273545972.$
$17^{1/3}$	-	$13^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.2199469029.$
$37^{1/3}$	-	$31^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.1908411993.$
$127^{1/3}$	-	$113^{1/3}$	$\approx 0.191938.$

$$4) D_n = p_{n+1}^a - p_n^a < 1/n, \quad (4)$$

where $a < a_0$ and n big enough, $n = n(a)$, holds for infinitely many consecutive primes.

a) Is this still available for $a < 1$?

b) Is there any rank n_0 depending on a and n such that (4) is verified for all $n \geq n_0$?

A few examples:

$5^{0.8}$	-	$3^{0.8}$	$\approx 1.21567.$
$7^{0.8}$	-	$5^{0.8}$	$\approx 1.11938.$
$11^{0.8}$	-	$7^{0.8}$	$\approx 2.06621.$
$127^{0.8}$	-	$113^{0.8}$	$\approx 4.29973.$
$307^{0.8}$	-	$293^{0.8}$	$\approx 3.57934.$
$997^{0.8}$	-	$991^{0.8}$	$\approx 1.20716.$

$$5) P_{n-1}/P_n \leq 5/3, \quad (5)$$

the maximum occurs at $n=2$.

{The ratio of two consecutive primes is limited, while the

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difference $p_{n+1} - p_n$ can be as big as we want!}

However, $1/p_n - 1/p_{n+1} \leq 1/6$, and the maximum occurs at $n=1$.

Reference:

[1] Sloane, N. J. A., Sequence A001223/M0296 in <An On-Line Version of the Encyclopedia of Integer Sequences>.

[“Octogon”, Braşov, Vol.7, No.1, 173-6, 1999.]